

Intellectual
Property
Office

Certificate of Registration for a UK Design

Design number: 6319466

Grant date: 08 November 2023

Registration date: 17 October 2023

This is to certify that,

in pursuance of and subject to the provision of Registered Designs Act 1949, the design of which a representation or specimen is attached, had been registered as of the date of registration shown above in the name of

Dr. Mohammed Rafiqkhan Khadhar Khan, Dr. Chinnasamy Balalakshmi, Dr.

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Ruban Packiasamy, Dr. Thota Suchitra Naidu, Mrs Mercy Thomson

in respect of the application of such design to:

PORTABLE NANOPARTICLE CYTOTOXICITY TESTER FOR CANCER

International Design Classification:

Version: 14-2023

Class: 24 MEDICAL AND LABORATORY EQUIPMENT

Subclass: 01 APPARATUS AND EQUIPMENT FOR DOCTORS, HOSPITALS
AND LABORATORIES

Adam Williams

Comptroller-General of Patents, Designs and Trade Marks

Intellectual Property Office

The attention of the Proprietor(s) is drawn to the important notes overleaf.

Representation of Designs

Intellectual Property Office is an operating name of the Patent Office

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